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Community Engagement Strategies For The Reduction Of Illegal Crude Oil Refining In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

Illegal crude oil refining also known as artisanal or illegal oil bunkering, poses significant environmental, social, and economic challenges in oil-producing regions, including Rivers State, Nigeria. This study aims to investigate the potential impact of host community engagement strategies in reducing illegal crude oil refining activities in Rivers State. The study examined the concept of community, community engagement. The study also outlined the reasons why illegal crude oil refining is thriving in the area, effects of the illegal crude oil refining on human and the environment. Data collection was primarily from secondary sources, including literature reviewed from articles, journals, textbooks, newspaper publications, periodicals, jingles which provided information for logical conclusions. Based on the reviewed literature, it was concluded that combating illegal artisanal oil refining requires a multifaceted and multi-stakeholder approach that is grounded in an informed understanding of both the problem and its context. The approach must include a combination of strategic, legal and regulatory measures, and policies that address the underlying social and economic dynamics, and should be guided by 'Do No Harm' principles to minimize second- and third-order consequences. For the approach to be effective it must be holistic, including policies that prioritize the creation of alternative economic opportunities in the formal and informal sectors where artisanal refining skills and technologies could be harnessed. It should also include environmental education to promote environmental sustainability and a communication strategy to raise public awareness of the negative impacts of illegal artisanal oil refining. The host community power blocks must be the primary drivers of this movement of change. The study suggested that Community youth must be enlightened and empowered through vocational training and environmental education to also ameliorate the situation. In supporting the local communities to fight against this menace, the government should cleanse degraded sites, afforestation and reforestation of degraded sites as well as free and compulsory environmental education for all the youths in Rivers State and the Niger Delta region. In addition, the government should strengthen the existing laws against illegal oil refining and increase non-compromising security surveillance around the affected areas in collaboration with community and youth leadership that is non-negotiable. The government and relevant organizations should also implement effective public awareness campaigns to reduce illegal crude oil refining by educating about the dangers, providing alternative livelihoods, emphasizing legal consequences, and utilizing various communication channels.

Keywords: Community, Engagement Strategies, illegal Crude oil

INTRODUCTION

A community is formed based on goals, aims and objectives which influences the kind of inhabitants that live and activities that are carried out in such a community. The word 'community' according to Warner in Kobani and Mba (2022) denotes a number of people, large or small sharing certain common interest, sentiments, behavioural patterns and other similarities by virtue of their belonging to a social group in a given territory. They further stated that a community with regards to development purposes can be determined and classified by peculiarity of the environment of habitation of the people, unique social needs of a group of people, or the nature of threat affecting the people. It should however, be noted that intentions, functions, goals, work, interest, aspirations, beliefs, culture, occupation, value-orientation, world view etc. have created more communities than territorial boundary has.

Community engagement work requires an understanding of the identified community and local issues, a listening environment, and continuous communication. It includes multiple opportunities for collecting citizen input through interaction and dialogue and identification of local solutions. Most importantly, public involvement must be focused with a defined purpose, clear expectations, an intentional planning process, and anticipated impacts.

According to Walker (2020) a community would be engaged in work that will impact that community. However, many times decisions are made for a community without that community providing any insight or offering any comments. Innovative leaders practice exclusion and are proactive to include all the stakeholders during the planning and decision making process. A proactive leader first defines the community and then begins the process of engaging that community in a conversation.

Although community development has its roots in nearly a century of practice and research, it is only since the mid-90's that community development researchers realized that to address larger and more complex societal issues, community members need to be more involved in the development process. One such awareness for greater involvement stemmed from Putnam's wake-up call in "Bowling Alone: America's Declining Social Capital" (1995) where Putnam cited American's declining civic engagement and social networks. What has since evolved is the theory and practice of Community Engagement. Virginia Cooperative Extension's experience with numerous leaders in Virginia's cities and counties suggests that the innovative leader designs inclusive processes and values the presence of multiple stakeholders during the planning and decision-making process. The Virginia experience supports the views of a majority of municipal leaders from across the United States, as documented in the 2010 National League of Cities report, "Making Local Democracy Work: Municipal Officials' Views About Public Engagement" (Barnes and Mann, 2010).

Why Illegal Refining of Crude Oil is Thriving in Rivers State

Illegal refining of crude oil is often encouraged by several factors, and scholars have identified some of these factors. Poverty is considered a significant driver of the illegal refining of crude oil (Nwilo & Badejo, 2019). According to them, poverty is a significant factor that encourages engagement in the illegal refining of crude oil. Another factor that encourages engagement in the illegal refining of crude oil is corruption (Oyegoke, 2019). Some individuals engage in the behavior to evade taxes and make quick profits. The corrupt practices of government officials and law enforcement agencies also contribute to the problem by creating an enabling environment for the practice to thrive. In addition, the lack of government presence and infrastructural development in the Niger Delta region has encouraged the engagement in illegal refining of crude oil (Akpan, 2018). The neglect of the region by the government has led to a lack of employment opportunities and social amenities, which has made illegal refining of crude oil an attractive alternative. Furthermore, some individuals engage in the illegal refining of crude oil because they believe it is a means of getting back at the government for the neglect of their region (Uzundu & Nwokedi, 2019). This is often due to the belief that the government is benefiting from the oil resources in the region at the expense of the local communities. Poverty, corruption, lack of government

presence and infrastructural development, and the desire for revenge against the government have been identified as some of the factors that encourage engagement in the illegal refining of crude oil.

Despite the various measures put in place to combat the illegal refining of crude oil in Rivers State, the problem persists. The existing approaches have primarily focused on law enforcement, which has often resulted in clashes between law enforcement agencies and illegal refiners, leading to loss of lives and property, and sometimes exacerbating the problem. Additionally, there has been a lack of comprehensive community engagement in combating illegal crude oil refining or the existence of some fractions of the community being part of the illegal crude oil refining and lack of public awareness campaigns to educate the local communities about the dangers of illegal refining of crude oil and the need for sustainable alternatives. This study tried to address these issues by investigating the impact of community engagement strategies for the reduction of illegal refining of crude oil in Rivers State.

Community Engagement

Engagement of the community is sometimes difficult to define and especially difficult to measure. For most projects, engagement means that the individual understands the purpose of the initiative, develops a sense of ownership, commits to the process and the outcome, and works toward achieving success (CDC, 1997). Community engagement was given a working definition by the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)(2011) when its first edition of Principles was published. The organization agreed that community engagement was: ...the process of working collaboratively with and through groups of people affiliated by geographic proximity, special interest, or similar situations to address issues affecting the well-being of those people. It is a powerful vehicle for bringing about environmental and behavioral changes that will improve the health of the community and its members. It often involves partnerships and coalitions that help mobilize resources and influence systems, change relationships among partners, and serve as catalysts for changing policies, programs, and practices (CDC, 1997, p 9 – published in CDC, Principles of Community Engagement Second Edition, 2011, p. 3). As defined by the CDC, “the goals of community engagement are to build trust, enlist new resources and allies, create Community Engagement, better communication, and improve overall health outcomes as successful projects evolve into lasting collaborations” (CDC, 2011).

A more recent definition states that community engagement “means people working collaboratively, through inspired action and learning, to create and realize bold visions for their common future.” (Born, 2012). In both instances, collaboratively working together toward a common issue or future is key to the community engagement process. The goals of community engagement are to build trust and relationships that lead to longstanding collaborations and, ultimately, positive impacts that improve the lives of the community members.

According to (CDC, 2011), nine key principles are needed that will help leaders and organizations form effective engagement processes and partnerships. These principles are divided into three categories: What items to consider prior to starting, what items are necessary for engagement, and what items are needed for successful engagement.

Before starting to work with a community:

1. **Defined purposes, goals and populations.** Researchers and organizers need to clearly state what the purpose of the community activity is to be.
2. **Know the community.** It is important to do the research and learn about the community, its culture, social networks, economic conditions, demographics, history and experiences.

Items necessary for engagement:

3. **Go to the community.** Engagement is a community process and the community will have greater opportunity for success if its members are an integral part of the development and implementation process. First, meet with key leaders and groups in their surroundings to ascertain their concerns, issues and barriers to participation. Depending on the goals of the activity, a small group of key stakeholders may be the most successful approach.

4. **Look for collective self-determination.** Community and individual self-determination are central to the community engagement process. Researchers need to help communities identify their own issues, name the problem, develop action areas, implement strategies and evaluate outcomes. The engagement process can be complex, with multiple factions providing diverse views and ideas.

Succeeding in the engagement process:

5. **Community partnerships are critical.** Opportunity for effective engagement includes equitable community partnerships and transparent discussions on power and decision-making. Partnering individuals and organizations should help to identify co-learning opportunities, contribution levels and how they will gain from the engagement partnership.

6. **Respect community diversity and culture.** Diversity can be related to economics, education, employment or health. Culture can be defined by language, race, ethnicity, age, gender, literacy or other personal interests. Diversity and culture may affect individual and community participation in the engagement process. Processes, strategies, and techniques should be used to engage individuals so that participation barriers are minimized and community cultures and norms celebrated.

7. **Mobilize community assets and develop capacity.** Community assets will vary depending on the individuals and organizations present. Individual interests, skills and experiences, as well as, social networks are assets that can be built into the engagement process.

8. **Maintain Flexibility.** The community engagement process can lead to changes in individuals and their respective organizations.

9. **Commitment to Collaboration.** Community engagement may be short-lived and centered on a specific initiative. However, long-term partnerships have the greatest potential for successful outcomes that affect complex societal issues. To sustain progress, partners should develop strategies to maintain collaborations and progress.

Crude Oil Refining in Rivers State

Crude oil was first discovered in Nigeria in large quantity in 1956 and 1958 respectively in Olibiri and Umuechem. Agriculture was the major means of livelihood of the people of Rivers State before the discovery of crude oil. From all indication, these discoveries of oil in 1956 became a blessing and at the same time a curse to the people of this South-south region due to the environmental degradation that came with oil exploration (Mezie-okoye, 2022).

The exploration of oil and gas in the region necessitate the location of foreign and local oil and gas companies to the region, therefore providing accommodation to transportation fleets, drilling equipment, and technological devices, that help the extraction of crude oil from land or sea within the Niger Delta region (Soremi, 2020). The activities of these oil companies in the region and the unconcerned attitudes towards the oil-beraing communities made The United Nations Development Programme (2012) to report that; "The greatest problem identified in the Niger Delta is poverty. In spite of the vast earnings from the region's oil and gas deposits, the region remains the second poorest region in the country where about 70% of the people are living below poverty line, and the poverty level in the region is well above the African standard. Both the federal government and oil companies operating in the region have failed to take necessary action to check the rampant environmental degradation in the region. There are over two million youths that are unemployed, seem to have lost hope, faith, and dignity in life due idleness. It is out of not knowing what to do to eke out life that pushed many youths into illegal refining, and cultism. There is urgent need for the health and wellbeing of these people, and the region to be saved from further environmental deterioration.

It is against this setback of severe environmental degradation, pollution, youth unemployment, extreme poverty that the artisanal refiners raised their ugly heads. According to Pallavi, Alexander and Fyneface (2022) the artisanal oil industry in Nigeria refers to the theft of crude for onward sale or local refining.

The term 'artisanal' belies the relatively complex, illegal and polluting nature of the industry. It has grown and formalized substantially, increased in sophistication along the value chain, and in places is run by large unions or cartels who have significant leverage in local and provincial government politics. Artisanal oil industry sites are mostly operative in Rivers, Bayelsa and Delta states, though they are also found in other oil-producing states in Nigeria's south. These are the three states where refineries are most concentrated, the technology of production is most advanced, and the political economy at the local, regional and national levels appear most intertwined. Rivers and Bayelsa produce around 21% and 18% respectively of Nigeria's crude oil (Golden, 2022). The sites use stolen crude as their raw material. Between 2015 and 2021, oil theft and repairs of oil pipelines from which crude was stolen cost the Nigerian economy at least \$29 billion. The daily loss amounts to 200,000 barrels per day (Addeh, 2022). The artisanal oil industry value chain involves 'tapping', whereby oil is diverted from pipelines to illegal exporters and artisanal oil industry refiners. Oil theft through such means is informally known as 'bunkering'. The oil is then transported by boats (which are hard to target in Niger Delta's dense, estuarine, mangrove-covered topography), for use either in artisanal oil industry sites or to be mixed with better-quality crude for sale on the black market. The crude in the artisanal oil industry site is 'cooked' in ovens where crude products or polluting. These 'refined' products are then transported by river or road to markets in the local communities, other states in the South-South and, according to anecdotal reports, even further afield to states such as Anambra, Imo and Abia in the South-East (Pallavi, Alexander and Fyनेface, 2022).

The Nigerian government's response to bunkering and, to a lesser extent, artisanal oil industry activities has been swift, persistent and highly militarized. Activities in the industry are illegal in Nigeria, and the Nigerian army and navy (Joint Task Force) have launched periodic offences against sites via operations named Operation River Sweep, Operation Calm Waters, Operation Swift Response, Operation Crocodile Smile, Operation Delta Safe, and Operation Quiet Waters. Camps have also been 'decommissioned' leading to further pollution, as the methods used include setting sites on fire. However, this has only led to the rise of armed militia such as the Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force (NDPVF) and the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) in the early 2000s, and the Niger Delta Avengers (NDA) in later decades, from within these local communities. Their conflicts with the military have been responsible for some of the most violent militant movements in Nigeria (Asuni, 2009).

However, some of these activities, especially in the artisanal oil industry, enjoy the support of many local communities. This would seem counterintuitive given the violence and Mitigation and transformation solutions to networked corruption in artisanal refining in the Niger Delta: retooling anti-corruption analysis for effective policy instability they have to face, both from security forces and the militant groups, as well as the effects of pollution from artisanal oil industry sites. While oil spills by international oil companies that have not been cleaned are chiefly to blame for damaging the delicate and complex ecosystem of the Niger Delta, micro-level pollution from the artisanal oil industry is also a contributory factor to water and air pollution in the region. The reasons for their persistence, despite these adverse outcomes, are twofold. First, bunkering and artisanal oil industry operations are part of well-organised and powerful political syndicates or networks that can include members of security forces, members of government organizations such as the Niger Delta Development Commission, and even politicians who can use these illegal proceeds to fund elections. Fighting elections is costly in Nigeria, especially for the posts of president and governors. The Financial Times reported that it costs \$2 billion to fight presidential elections in the country (Pilling, 2022). While not as costly as a presidential election, it would be safe to say gubernatorial elections would also be very costly for candidates. Illegal activities in the artisanal oil industry sector provide the required funding for many such political activities.

The second reason why these activities persist is that artisanal oil industry sites provide both direct and indirect livelihoods to some of Nigeria's most impoverished populations. While estimates of per capita incomes of Nigerian states are not easy to come by, one study based on extrapolating social indicators found that Rivers and Delta were in the top five performers, while Bayelsa ranked at 27 out of 37

(Igbokwe, 2017). Despite this, Rivers had an unemployment rate of over 40% and Bayelsa and Delta had a rate of over 30%. These rates are high when compared to non-oil states such as Benue, Kebbi and Osun (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2021). These three oil-bearing states do not score as high on the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) when compared to their per capita incomes and, indeed, to other states that are not oil-rich (Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative (OPHI), 2017). Rivers and Bayelsa also had the lowest rank, according to the Human Security Index, in the economic domain, though they do rank higher in some other aspects, such as education (UNDP, 2015).

Effects of Illegal Oil Refining in Rivers State

Effects of Illegal Oil Refining on the Environment

In the submission of Pallavi, et al. (2022) despite the fact that the Niger Delta region is rich in oil and gas deposits; it also has very rich, fertile, and diverse wetland vegetation. Wetlands are ecosystems naturally endowed with distinct and special characteristics. They are an important environmental resource of the world with high biota. They are classified into marshes, swamps, and bogs depending on the vegetation type, salinity of water, and soil type. Prominent among them is the mangrove swamp vegetation wetland. The Niger Delta mangrove vegetation is the largest in Africa and the sixth-largest in the world (Chindah, Braide, Amakiri, & Onokurhefe, 2007), with up to 0.8 million ha of mangrove stands in this area constituting about 35% of all West African mangroves (FAO., 1981).

Source: (Photo by Orji Sunday in Pallavi, Alexander & Fyneface (2022)).

The black soot that plagues the city of Port Harcourt has been linked to artisanal refining of stolen crude oil. The anthropogenic activities have devastated a large proportion of the wetland vegetation of the Niger Delta over the years. It is estimated that crude oil theft (commonly called illegal bunkering) accounts for between 200,000 and 300,000 barrels of crude oil daily lost in Nigeria; with a significant proportion of the stolen oil going into artisanal refining in make-shift facilities into low-quality petroleum products (Naanen, 2012). The inefficiency of the process is so much that it is most likely that as much as 80% of the heavy end of the crude oil cannot be refined and is just discharged into the environment (Attah, 2012). It is during the process of stealing the crude oil from pipelines and illegally refining it that great environmental and economic devastation is done to the environment. It is this activity of these local refiners that devastated the communities' environment that their traditional means of livelihood such as farming and fishing are destroyed. This illegal refining also poses serious health risks (SDN, 2012). The

UNEP (2011) reported several incidents of artisanal refining activity in Ogoni land that cause fire accidents, and the destruction of the ecosystem.

Effect on Human Health

Members of the society are exposed to a variety of health risks as a result of illegal refiners' activities. Port Harcourt and its environs have been affected by the current issue of black soot. Black soot is a small particle that can penetrate deep into the lungs and has been associated with a variety of catastrophic health impacts in children, including premature death, heart attacks, and strokes, as well as acute bronchitis, and worsened asthma. PM 2.5 –particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less – is the popular name for a type of particle pollution known as soot. These tiny particles are even smaller than dust and mold, measuring around 1/30 of the width of a human hair. It is made up of a range of contaminants such as chemicals, acids, metals, soils, and dust that are suspended in the air after they are released. Soot can exist in three states: solid, liquid, and gaseous (“aerosols”). I recalled that when you washed your clothes and hung them to dry, they would have black stains by the time you returned (researcher's experience, 2020).

Effect of Illegal Oil Refining on Security

Illegal oil bunkering and artisanal refining are major drivers of insecurity in the oil and gas industry and the agricultural sector in the Niger Delta. Vandalism and illegal tapping of oil pipelines by criminal gangs have compelled oil firms to regularly declare force majeure on oil and gas exports thereby undercutting profits and reducing government revenue (Daily Trust, May 15, 2022). According to data, Thisday Newspaper, January 31, 2022, the Nigerian government reportedly loses an average of 200,000 barrels of crude oil per day, which is more than 10 per cent of daily production, and an estimated \$4 billion yearly as a result of illegal oil bunkering and artisanal oil refining activities in the Niger Delta.

Other Devastating Effects Resulting from Illegal Crude Oil Refining in Rivers State

According to **Dennis (2022) re-examines the soot menace in Port Harcourt and its environs, the root of the problem and what must be done urgently to effectively combat the problem. He had these to report:** The thick black smoke that billows up into the sky almost on a daily basis has become a common sight in Port Harcourt, the Rivers State capital, and its outskirts. In many parts of the metropolis, the atmosphere is usually foggy from as early as 7am, and this has become a daily occurrence. More often than not, residents wake up to these toxic hydrocarbon emissions emanating from surrounding creeks and waterways and hanging in the air for hours. A visitor would easily conclude that a heavy rainfall was looming, but to the residents who have become used to the situation, it's a sad reminder of an environmental problem that has refused to go away. The evidence of the problem is everywhere. Outside a house, one is easily coated with the soot – black powder – and while inside, mere cleaning of the floor, furniture, electronics, sanitary ware and other household items shows the extent of the spread. While some claimed the soot had been there since illegal refining became a popular activity, it became more noticeable in Port Harcourt about five years ago when suddenly the atmosphere became dark in broad daylight.

Beyond the stains on the surface of items, the health of the residents may also be taking a hit. For example, by cleaning one's face or nostrils with white handkerchief, one is assured of a black stain. Sadly, this dangerous smoke has engulfed Abonnema Wharf, Borikiri, Amadi and Abuloma in the Garden City and has spread to Emuoha, Onne, Gokana, Okrika and Eleme Local Government Areas of the state. Since air has no boundary, it implies that the health of about seven million residents of Rivers State is now being threatened.

The soot has caused us so much discomfort and we don't even know the impact it would have on our health,” Blessing Ojei, a teacher and mother of four, told Saturday PUNCH. Ojei, who resides in the old Port Harcourt township axis, said she had been constrained to clean her house and mop the floor on a daily basis because the black smoke easily covers all surfaces. She added, “Everywhere in the house is covered by black smoke. Catarrh has become a regular occurrence for my children and me. Even when

one spits, it comes out black. If you put your hand inside your nose, it is black. “Our environment has become so polluted and it doesn’t matter whether or not the windows are closed, air will always find its way into the house. All our furniture, electronics and sanitary ware are affected. “I wash our mosquito nets every two days, otherwise once the children sleep in it, it would give them catarrh. Meanwhile, we can’t stop using the nets because of mosquitoes.”

Comparatively, Ojei has been lucky. Hers hasn’t resulted in serious ailment, but Miss Favour Punen hasn’t been so lucky, as she said two of her nieces, aged seven and 10, had fallen ill and were taken to the hospital on account of inhaling the polluted air. She said she had since resorted to wearing her face masks to limit the volume of the substances she inhales. Punen, who resides in Elekahia area of Port Harcourt, said, “The floor of the house is usually dusty and it is when you check underneath your feet – for those of us who love to walk with bare feet at home – or you use a wet cloth to mop the floor that you see how black it is. “Even when you mop, moments later, the black powder would have taken over the entire space again. It’s the same way your fingers turn black when you put them in your nose. Whenever I’m going out I wear my face mask because it makes me susceptible to catarrh. “My two nieces had runny noses and catarrh. We even took them to the hospital where they were given antibiotics and some immune boosters. It was after that they felt better. It’s a serious problem that the government needs to address urgently. Sometimes we see this thick smoke during the day and have to quickly close the windows and stay indoors until it is clear outside.”

These are only a fraction of what the residents of the state have been subjected to over time. But the impending question is, what the local communities can do to support government efforts to reduce and possibly eradicate the illegal crude oil refining in Rivers State that has caused a lot environmental problems to humans, plants and animals in the State and its environs.

The Way Forward

According to Channels Live TV on the 8th of January, 2022, The Governor of Rivers State declared 19 individuals wanted for operating illegal crude oil refining sites which are responsible for black soot menace in Rivers State. Having the concern and wellbeing of Rivers People at heart, The Governor, also mandated the 23 local government chairmen in the state to provide a comprehensive list of illegal refineries and their operators within their jurisdiction, noted that it would be unwise for a responsible government to fold its arms and do nothing to safeguard the residents of the state.

Wike said, “It’s unfortunate for this country that security people will be involved in illegal bunkering. I can’t believe it. Mr. CP (Commissioner of Police), I thank you for transferring the DPO in Rumuji, who owns a refinery. But the man must leave here, not be transferred. He must leave this state. In the exact words of the Governor “I can’t be governor here and a security man owns an illegal refinery. No, it is not possible. The man has to go. Take him to wherever they allow bunkering.” While demanding for the transfer of the NSCDC personnel in charge of vandalisation of pipelines in the state, Wike said he once intercepted a Major in the army providing escort for illegally refined petroleum products. “We must continue to take this war (against illegal oil refining and bunkering) very seriously, not only because it is sabotage to the national economy but also for the health of our people, which for me is key.”

The most affected group of the hazardous effects of illegal crude oil refining is the host community. Farmlands have been destroyed, fishing settlements evacuated as a result of pollution of the rivers and estuaries with loss of lives and properties. This is the single most reason why the communities where the illegal refineries are situated must speak up by reporting these activities to appropriate authorities to enforce the eradication of refineries in the state and restore the natural state of the environment to allow for regeneration of the biodiversity, aesthetic scenery of the forest, plants species, wildlife habitat, water cycles and medicinal plant species.

Community youth must be enlightened and empowered through vocational training and environmental education to also ameliorate the situation. In supporting the local communities to fight against this menace, the government should cleanse degraded sites, afforestation and reforestation of degraded sites as

well as free and compulsory environmental education for all the youths in Rivers State and the Niger Delta region. In addition, the government should strengthen the existing laws against illegal oil refining and increase non-compromising security surveillance around the affected areas in collaboration with community and youth leadership that is non-negotiable.

In a study conducted by Nwachukwu and Tumba (2023), they recommended public awareness and one of the strategies to reducing the illegal crude oil refining in Rivers State. To effectively reduce the illegal refining of crude oil, targeted public awareness campaigns are needed to address the factors that influence engagement in the behavior. Several strategies have been suggested for improving public awareness campaigns on this issue. Community-based approaches: have been found to be effective in improving public awareness about the dangers of illegal refining of crude oil. A study by Ako and Ufot (2018) found that community-based approaches such as town hall meetings, focus group discussions, and community mobilization can effectively reach specific communities and address their unique concerns. By engaging with local communities in this way, public awareness campaigns can be tailored to specific contexts and more effectively communicate the dangers associated with the illegal refining of crude oil. Traditional media such as radio and television: have also been found to be effective in disseminating information about the dangers of illegal refining of crude oil. Studies have shown that traditional media can reach a large audience, particularly in rural areas where internet access may be limited (Omeje, 2019; Enekwe & Ezeah, 2018). By using these channels, public awareness campaigns can effectively reach a broad audience and raise awareness about the risks associated with the illegal refining of crude oil. Social media platforms: such as Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp have also been suggested as a strategy to improve public awareness campaigns. According to Emenike and Nwachukwu (2018), social media platforms can be used to engage and educate a large number of people, particularly young people who are more likely to be tech-savvy and active on social media.

By using these platforms, public awareness campaigns can reach a wider audience, and can also encourage community members to share information with their social networks. In addition to these strategies, there is a need for the development of targeted messages that resonate with the target audience. Messages should be tailored to address the specific concerns and motivations of the target audience. A study by Obi and Obi (2019) found that messages that emphasized the health and environmental consequences of illegal refining of crude oil were more effective in improving public awareness than messages that focused solely on the legal and economic implications. By implementing these strategies, public awareness campaigns on the dangers of illegal refining of crude oil can be improved, and more effectively address the factors that encourage engagement in this behavior.

All the above recommendations will be meaningless if after implementation, our refineries are not revived. Indeed, it is possible to contend that our own moribund refineries have largely created the vacuum the operators of the illegal refineries are attempting to fill.

CONCLUSION

Combating illegal artisanal oil refining requires a multifaceted and multi-stakeholder approach that is grounded in an informed understanding of both the problem and its context. The approach must include a combination of strategic, legal and regulatory measures, and policies that address the underlying social and economic dynamics, and should be guided by 'Do No Harm' principles to minimize second- and third-order consequences. For the approach to be effective it must be holistic, including policies that prioritize the creation of alternative economic opportunities in the formal and informal sectors where artisanal refining skills and technologies could be harnessed. It should also include environmental education to promote environmental sustainability and a communication strategy to raise public awareness of the negative impacts of illegal artisanal oil refining. The host community power blocks must be the primary drivers of this movement of change.

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